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D9.4 – Stakeholder workshop

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REPORT

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Table of Contents

Table of Contents	3
1 Executive Summary	5
2 Introduction.....	5
3 Programme and organisation.....	6
3.1 Programme	6
3.2 Organisation	7
4 Outcome.....	11
4.1 Presentations and discussions.....	11
4.1.1 Session 1: End-user perspectives on bio-based innovations	11
4.1.2 Session 2: Making Bio-based Compounds	13
4.1.3 Session 3: Sustainability, Safety and Toxicity.....	15
4.1.4 Session 4: Industrial Applications	17
4.2 Use of interactive tool for Q&A	21
5 Dissemination activities and networking	22
5.1 Poster presentations	22
5.2 Exhibition of materials.....	23
5.3 The Green Kid comic book.....	24
5.4 Networking opportunities	24
6 Conclusions.....	25
Annex 1: Overview of participating organisations.....	26
Annex 2: Shared CHAMPION-PERFECOAT press release	27
Annex 3: Event flyer	28
Annex 4: Event agenda	29
Annex 5: Presentations at the stakeholder event	30
Annex 6: Posters presented at the poster session	31

Annex 7: CHAMPION’s issue of the Green Kid comic 32

1 Executive Summary

This report describes the stakeholder event ‘Bio-based Innovations for Industrial Applications’ that was organised as the final stakeholder workshop within the CHAMPION project. The event was organised on 24 April 2024 in Brussels, in close cooperation with the PERFECOAT project.

The document provides a summary of the activities organised ahead of and during the event as well as practical information about the event.

2 Introduction

The CHAMPION project focuses on innovations to support a circular economy. While on the one hand the project consortium was geared to bring together high quality expertise as to support its innovative work, the consortium partners on the other hand also recognised from the early stages of the project that to bring its targeted innovations to market required wider dissemination of the results to academia and the public. One of the means to this end was the organisation of the stakeholder event as to inform a wider audience on the achievements to date, as well as to discuss the opportunities and challenges to bringing the CHAMPION products to market.

Recognising that a wide range of expertise will be needed in future steps in development, the project team had decided that the stakeholder event would not only focus on the CHAMPION project results, but also offer a platform for sibling projects with related aims. The main aims of this partnering were to enrich the discussion and broaden the knowledge base. The objectives of the stakeholder event therewith were not only to transfer the knowledge obtained in the project towards relevant researchers and industry stakeholders, but also to generate scientific discussions and increase the opportunities to identify follow-up actions to bring the innovations to market.

The stakeholder event was originally targeted to be organised 4 months prior to the targeted completion of the project. With the project duration being extended and the realisation that follow-up possibilities were best served when tangible project results could be shared, the consortium had decided to organise the event a month before the completion of the project.

The event was held in Brussels on 24 April 2024 and attracted 111 participants from 85 organisations. Participation at the event was free of charge with mandatory registration. An overview of the organisations attending the stakeholder event is included in Annex 1.

3 Programme and organisation

3.1 Programme

The event took place from 9 am to 5 pm and consisted of four themed sessions of presentations and discussions, followed by a poster exhibition and networking cocktail. Participants were welcomed by Janice Lofthouse from the University of York, on behalf of the CHAMPION project and Francesca di Bartolomeo from SINTEF, on behalf of the PERFECOAT project. The closing statement was provided by James Clark from the University of York's Green Chemistry Centre of Excellence, co-ordinator of the CHAMPION project.

When developing the programme, the organisation team aimed to provide the audience with a broad range of expertise and also offer a platform to sibling projects HARMONITOR, 3-Co and LIGNICOAT.

Session 1: End-user perspectives on bio-based innovations

Event opening by Janice Lofthouse (University of York – CHAMPION) and Francesca di Bartolomeo (SINTEF – PERFECOAT)

An overview of the CHAMPION project by Daan van Es (WFBR)

An introduction to the PERFECOAT project by Francesca di Bartolomeo (SINTEF)

Navigating Trade and Sustainability Certification of Bio-based Value Chains by Marisa Groenestegé (BTG Biomass Technology Group – HARMONITOR project)

What Drives Sustainability in Business by Costanza Rossi (University of Utrecht – 3-Co project)

Panel Q&A session 1

Session 2: Making Bio-based Compounds

Developing Bio-based Binders for Wood Coatings by Oscar Bedzo (Celignis)

Bio-based Polymer Synthesis and Scale-up by Rolf Blaauw (WFBR)

Developing Bio-based Paint Ingredients: from Fillers to Pigments and Functional Additives by Amelie Skopp (Technische Universität München) and Anders Odum (Chromologics SA)

Lignin-based Clear Fire Protection Biocoatings for Wood by Claudio Pagella (IRIS Coating – LIGNICOAT)

Panel Q&A session 2

Session 3: Sustainability, Safety and Toxicity
Safety and Toxicity Assessments and Methodology by Harrie Besselink (BioDetection Systems) and Andy Booth (SINTEF)
Environmental and Social Sustainability Assessment by Ángel Puente (nova-Institute) and Assiya Kenzhegaliyeva (SINTEF Digital)
Circularity and End-of-life Options for Bio-based and Biodegradable Products by Steven Verstichel (Normec OWS)
Panel Q&A session 3

Session 4: Industrial Applications
Industrial Aspects of the EU Bioeconomy Policy Framework: Recent Developments by Maarit Nyman and Algreit Dume (European Commission)
Circular Bio-Based Europe JU: Supporting Innovation of Sustainable Bio-based Materials and Products by Chloe Johnson (CBE JU)
End-user Application Testing of Polymers in CHAMPION by Thomas Farmer (Unilever)
Bio-based Coating Formulation and Application Testing by Simone Schulte (Evonik Coating Additives)
Panel Q&A session 4

3.2 Organisation

In preparation of the stakeholder event the CHAMPION task coordinator had identified the potential added value of widening discussions to not only addressing CHAMPION project results and ambitions, but also addressing related topics that were researched in sibling projects. The team therefore contacted the PERFECOAT project with a proposal for a joint event. The PERFECOAT project was identified as the ideal candidate for this, given their similar focus on supporting the circular economy by means of a higher application of bio-based products. In addition, to further strengthen discussions at the event, sibling projects were offered to present their work. Invitations were extended to the 3-Co and HARMONITOR project that work on certification schemes and labels for bio-based products and value chains, and to the LIGNICOAT project that – as PERFECOAT – also works to develop sustainable coatings.

The organisation of the event was coordinated by SQ Consult (on behalf of the CHAMPION project) and nova Institut (on behalf of PERFECOAT). UOY as the overall coordinator of the CHAMPION project was involved as reviewer and in decision making, with SINTEF playing that role on the PERFECOAT side. The partners had in an early stage agreed on which partner was responsible for arranging which item on the agenda and attracting the best possible speaker for

each of the presentations. SQ Consult was responsible for selecting the event location and all related logistic arrangements such as organisation of the poster session and the catering. Nova Institut coordinated dissemination activities, including design of the flyer. The costs of the event were shared between the two coordinating parties.

After some initial discussions between CHAMPION and PERFECOAT and settling on Brussels as the location for the event, in August 2023 we reached out to the CBE JU communications team to ask when the next CBE JU info day was planned. Our plan was to organise our event immediately before or after the CBE JU Info Day, giving participants the opportunity to attend both events in a single trip. Upon learning the CBE Info Day 2024 would be held on 23 April, the project team decided on 24 April for the stakeholder event. We anticipated that this would not only have a positive effect on the number of participants attending both events, but also reduce the environmental and financial travel costs for participants planning to attend both events. For similar reasons, both CHAMPION and PERFECOAT held their general assemblies the day after the event, in the case of CHAMPION this avoided an international trip for about 20 people, some of which also attended the CBE JU Info Day.

The [webpage for the event and the registration system](#) were prepared and hosted by nova Institute, and launched on 16 November 2023, together with a banner for the event.

**Bio-based
Innovations
for Industrial Applications**
24 April 2024, 09:00–17:00 CET

**BIP Meeting Center,
Rue Royale 2-4, B-1000 Brussels**
Free Registration • In-person Event

These projects receive funding from the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 897398 and No 101022370. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

The event was first announced on CHAMPION's social media channels ([LinkedIn](#), [X](#) and [Facebook](#)) and website on 27 November 2023. CHAMPION partners started announcing the event through their digital channels and at events they were attending as well and the [PERFECOAT](#) and [LIGNICOAT](#) projects also announced the event around the same time.

Following additional announcements on social media, such as with preliminary agenda and further updates, PERFECOAT and [CHAMPION launched a joint press release](#) to achieve a wide range of potential participants on 27 February 2024. The press release has been included as Annex 2.

D9.4 Stakeholder workshop

CBE JU also was also instrumental in announcing our event, not only through their social media posts but also through a dedicated webpage on the CBE JU website. At CHAMPION's request, CBE JU also included our event in several of their reminder emails about the CBE Info Days, therefore our event was easy to find for participants of the CBE Info Days. Likewise, CHAMPION highlighted the opportunity to combine the CBE Info Day and our event on our website and in various of our posts.

As a further way to attract attention and participants and for sharing on social media, a flyer was produced. The content of the flyer was discussed and agreed between partners, nova Institute designed the flyer and both projects engaged their project partners to share the flyer within their networks through social media. The flyer is included as Annex 3.

Substantial effort was put in achieving a very interesting agenda for the event:

- Four presentations by each project, plus 2 presentations in which CHAMPION and PERFECOAT presented jointly on shared topics: sustainability assessment and toxicological safety testing.
- Three sibling projects sharing their most interesting results so far: HARMONITOR, 3-CO and LIGNICOAT.
- Appropriate representation of the European Union: both the European Commission (DG GROW) and CBE JU held presentations.

The full agenda of the event has been included as Annex 4.

All our efforts in designing an event with clear added value and spreading the word more than paid off: the event was sold out on 10/04/2024. In order to ensure that every seat is filled with individuals eager to engage and contribute at our event, on 11/04/2024 we sent an email to all registered participants to confirm their attendance for the event, in order to ensure the most efficient use of both resources and seats. While over 100 people confirmed their attendance, we were also able to register about 15 additional people due to other registrants communicating that they unfortunately could not attend. Effectively the total number of registrations was 146 and the number of actual participants at the event was 111 representing at least 85 organisations, see Annex 1. Participants indicated their section, the largest group of participants were from industry, followed by the scientific community. The 15 people who indicated "Other" were mostly managers, business developers, consultants at small businesses or from international organizations. See figure Figure 1.

Figure 1 - stakeholder event attendees per sector

Organisation at the event day itself was shared between the projects, with PERFECOAT taking responsibility for the interactive Q&A tool Slido, collecting all presentation files on the computer used during the presentations, registration of participants, name tags, speaker name cards etc. and CHAMPION organising the posterboards and product samples in the poster room and getting presentations ready for the next presenter. Chairing of the event was also shared between the projects.

Immediately following the event, CHAMPION prepared a page on our website containing the presentations and posters from the event, and sent out a “thank you” email to all participants for making the event so successful and pointing to the page where the posters and presentations can be found: <https://www.champion-project.eu/stakeholder-event>.

4 Outcome

4.1 Presentations and discussions

This section provides a short summary of all presentations and discussion. The full presentations are included in Annex 5 of this report.

4.1.1 Session 1: End-user perspectives on bio-based innovations

After the official opening of the event, the two projects were introduced. Daan van Es from WFBR provided an overview of **the CHAMPION project**. He explained that the project aims to replace conventional polymers with novel bio-based polymers that are more sustainable, safer and at least equal in performance than the current materials. The project targeted four application areas: surface coatings, automotive interiors, structural adhesives and home care. Industry partners were included in the project for each of these application areas. After explaining the concept and the approach of the project Daan provided further details on the project methodology. CHAMPION partners have prepared several novel bio-based amines and Michael acceptors which have been polymerised with a view towards producing coatings and adhesives. In this hardness and flexibility of the polymers are tuned by varying the crosslinking density. Tests were conducted to compare the soil biodegradation of aza-Michael polymers with conventional radical-cured polymers. The results show that bio-based polymers have a good end of life performance when compared with the standard benchmark of cellulose.

Francesca di Bartolomeo from SINTEF explained that **the PERFECOAT project** specifically targets the market for coatings, since only 5% of the sales values in this market is occupied by bio-based systems and since this is a growing market. Similar to the CHAMPION project, the aims of PERFECOAT are to develop innovations that meet and even surpass the current quality and sustainability standards. PERFECOAT aims to develop and validate coatings with at least 25% bio-based components. The project is building and operating a modular and flexible technology platform for producing innovative bio-based binders, fillers and pigments. This is geared towards developing a complete value chain from substrate provision to industrial scale-up and quality assessments. Francesca concluded her presentation by pointing out that more detailed project presentations will be provided later in the day.

Next, the audience was provided with a summary of two projects that concentrate on certification schemes and labels (CSLs) for bio-based products and value chains. Marisa Groenestege from BTG presented the project working on Harmonisation and monitoring platform for certification

D9.4 Stakeholder workshop

schemes and labels to advance the sustainability of bio-based systems (**the HARMONITOR project**). She explained that the main ambition is to develop a platform in which CSLs can cooperate and be compared to support the use of CSLs as a co-regulation instrument. Next, she elaborated how the project is navigating trade flows of bio-based products and their level of certification. Marissa concluded by inviting the participants to check out the [trade flow tool](#) that is available on the project website.

Also **the 3-Co project** has the objective to develop a supportive framework for CSLs. In the final presentation of session 1, Costanza Rossi from Utrecht University/SQ Consult concentrated on the internal and external motivations for companies to obtain sustainability certification. The conclusion is that the main drivers of certification for companies are improved image and expected economic benefits. Costanza illustrated this by showing the main drivers of three different certification schemes regularly used on the market. Consumers have an increasing interest in sustainable bio-based products and have a higher willingness to pay for certified products. Yet there are barriers to certification, such as high costs, complex processes, insufficient expected benefits and proliferation of CSLs. To understand this better, 3-Co will conduct a survey to compare the real and expected benefits of certification.

In the **Q&A session** a wide range of topics were discussed, including:

- *Where do you see the main challenges in certifying bio-based products and feedstocks and how do you estimate the benefits?* The speaker responds that the challenges really vary per type of stakeholder and provided some examples for different types of stakeholders.
- *What is the percentage of the bio-based materials in the polyester developed in CHAMPION?* Some of the components are already fully bio-based while other formulations still contain a fossil derived compound that is in the development process to be fully bio-based. In the future the aim is to have the products fully bio-based.
- *What is the target size and scale in the CHAMPION project?* The audience is referred to the poster exhibition for this information.
- *Does the PERFECOAT project also test the properties for food packings and if so, what are the results?* This is not being tested at the moment, but that could be a project outcome in the future.

4.1.2 Session 2: Making Bio-based Compounds

In the second set of presentations, further details were presented on various project activities that are developing bio-based compounds. Oscar Bedzo from Celignis first provided information on developing bio-based binders for wood coatings in the **PERFECOAT project**. After presenting the requirements of UV curable binders for wood coatings and of water-based binders for architectural paints, he provided a summary of the various base components that are explored in developing bio-based binders and the various modifications analysed in the project. In the concluding remarks the speaker shares the team's expectation that the targeted bio-based binder concentration in their new formulated coatings will be in the range of 25-50 wt%.

Next Rolf Blaauw of WFBR presented the work on bio-based polymer synthesis and scale-up in the **CHAMPION project**. He explained that current thermoset chemistry is based on non-reversible polymers and has toxicity issues with (residual) monomers. The aza-Michael (AM) addition used in CHAMPION addresses these issues. One of the main conclusions is that two-component reactive resin formulations were developed in the CHAMPION project which may serve as safe and circular alternatives for PU and epoxy systems. Earlier tests with polyester diacrylate acceptors were not suitable for the end applications that the project was looking for, as the final product was not sufficiently strong and hard. The project was aiming for high shore D harness. Another issue encountered was that in few cases the after a few weeks the samples agglomerated, but this was solved by optimising primary diamines and optimized UPE/diamine ratios. The speaker shows the audience a range of photos from the lab-scale AM mixing and curing for thermosets developed and tested in the project.

Dr. Amélie Skopp from the Technical University of Munich and Anders Ødum from Chromologics SA provide the next presentation on work conducted in the **PERFECOAT project**, focusing on greener raw materials. Amélie started by showing that coatings are used everywhere in our daily lives and that the three main functions of coatings are protection, decoration and special properties such as water repellency. Of the different types of ingredients of coatings, the project is focusing on pigments, fillers and additives. The speaker illustrated various candidate filler materials that have been tested and the range of parameters that are being tested, including colour, gloss and scrub resistance. Interim results show that biomass can be used as extender alternative, but certain performance parameters need to be optimized. Results also show that using microbial cells as platform for functionalization is possible. In the second part of the presentation the speakers concentrated on the scale-up of precision fermentation for bio-based ingredients, illustrating the achievements over time and concluding that the long journey from screening to production requires careful thinking of process principles and overcoming many

challenges. After 11 years of work at Chromologics SA, the product development activities have reached a production scale of 100,000 litres.

Representing the **LIGNICOAT project**, Claudio Pagella from IRIS Coating presented the work conducted on lignin-based clear fire protection biocoatings for wood. To address industry's challenge to diminish the use of fossil-based coatings, the LIGNICOAT aims to demonstrate the technical and economic feasibility of the use of lignin as raw material to produce bio-resins for 3 coating specialties: wood fireproofing coatings, metal anticorrosion coatings, and antimicrobial hygienic coatings. Lignin was chosen as the focus of the research as it is one of the most abundant organic polymers on earth and the most abundant natural source of aromatic compounds. The project results show that lignin indeed provides a sustainable alternative compared to traditional fossil-based raw materials. The speaker shows the audience results of several tests on colour and fire performance and concludes that the project will most likely not result in just one product, but a portfolio of lignicoat coatings for various applications with a bio-based content of up to 60%.

The audience raised many questions during the **Q&A for session 2**, including:

- *What is the maximum fire the product can resist? How many degrees?* Standard material resistance to fire is measured in time, so how long can they stand temperatures of 550 degrees. Currently tests are conducted for temperatures up to 200-220 degrees and in these tests the materials perform similar as their fossil-based alternatives.
- *How are the new materials developed in PERFE COAT different than current commercially offered bio-based acrylate oligomers?* The focus is not to compare against currently available bio-based materials, but to improve against fossil-based materials.
- *Which one is the most promising in terms of performance and end of life. A variety of filler materials was tested. How to stabilise the natural fillers against moving?* There are some formulations where you are mixing the dry and liquid packets. Stabilising is done by adding acids or by limiting the amount of dye and water.
- *What is the source of the unsaturated polyesters and amines developed in the CHAMPION project?* Most are based on carbohydrates; all of them are based on compounds that exist in nature, but not all of them are yet commercially available.
- *Is the AM reaction reversible? If so, under*

which conditions? This depends on the specific polymer, but typically if you heat it up to approx. 150 degrees, see also the CHAMPION poster on chemical recycling.

- *Are the pigments developed in PERFECOAT only suitable for coatings or could they be applied in other areas such as textiles, cosmetics or food?* The natural colours are not yet so stable in the long-term, so textiles are not a good application yet. But some of them can be good solutions for cosmetics and food. For the latter there will be regulatory boundaries.
- *The structure of lignin can vary based on the type of wood, location of the crop, weather, etcetera. How colour consistent is the material?* We have observed quite large differences in colour, but we have not focused yet on linking this to specific backgrounds and origins.

4.1.3 Session 3: Sustainability, Safety and Toxicity

In a joint presentation for both the **CHAMPION and PERFECOAT projects** Harrie Besselink (BioDetection Systems) and Andy Booth (SINTEF) presented their work on safety and toxicity assessments and the methodologies used for these assessments. At the start, the speakers explained the reasons for safety and toxicity testing and the standard methods to conduct these. The projects use a different approach to conduct their assessments but neither uses animals. In CHAMPION safety testing is conducted by a cellular pathway-based approach, and in PERFECOAT by means of analytical chemistry.

In the presentation both speakers lead the audience through their approach and the results of the work. Both projects show that their approaches are cost-effective compared to classical methods and have high throughput, and therewith show potential for widespread use.

In another joint presentation Ángel Puente (nova-Institute) and Assiya Kenzhegaliyeva (SINTEF Digital) presented the environmental and social sustainability assessments conducted in the **CHAMPION and PERFECOAT project**. The speakers explained that sustainability assessments are at the core of both projects and illustrated how they have approached and completed their work. In the CHAMPION project the LCA has been used to support selection of the most promising candidates, for instance by flagging when serious sustainability concerns were identified when analysing potential candidates. In addition, the LCA guided the process development by identification of hotspots in the performance of candidates.

The PERFECOAT project focuses on the assessment of the social sustainability of bio-based solutions, an area for which there are limited current studies available. The speaker provided an overview of the preliminary results for the socio-political acceptance, the market acceptance and the community acceptance, identifying the main drivers, challenges and the possible directions how challenges could be addressed. The assessment of social impacts will be conducted for various segments of the value chain and for different stakeholder categories.

The speaker also explained that it is crucial to identify impacts as early as possible in order to steer further development of bio-based projects towards high sustainability.

Steven Verstichel from Normec OWS presented on circularity and end-of-life options for bio-based and biodegradable products that were analysed in the **CHAMPION project**. After an introduction on circularity, recycling and compostability, Steven presented the basics on biodegradation and presented applications in which biodegradation is a beneficial characteristic.

In a graphical presentation he showed that the polyesters crosslinked with AM chemistry show an improved biodegradation in soil compared to conventional radical crosslinking. Steven concludes that biodegradation receives more and more attention, also in EU policy and regulations.

The **Q&A for session 3** included:

- *Can the CALUX system check the activity in bio-based end products?* Yes, you can do migration studies also for end products, in which we prepare an extract, usually with a solvent. The activity of the compounds migrating out of the end product can then be tested; we cannot test solid materials directly.
- *How can we correlate the skin sensitization tests to actual effects on skin and tissues?* It is a relative assessment, the amount of responses correlates to the risk of toxicity. It is an exact replication of the exact reaction that would take place in the skin. It is not an approximation.
- *Is bio-based always sustainable? Do we still have issues to cover in bio-based value chains and if yes, what?* No, bio-based is not necessarily sustainable. You would have to prove that with studies. But in general, if you look into LCA, we can see that in most cases for the most relevant

impact areas bio-based products do a very good job compared to fossil-based systems and products. But to actually conclude that a bio-based product is sustainable a relative comparison is not sufficient, and you would also need to do an absolute comparison. That would require additional analysis, including field tests.

- *Which are the major obstacles in social acceptance and what are the main drivers to increase social acceptance?* The main obstacles are high prices and the origin of the biomass, including questions such as how does it contribute to the local communities producing raw materials. The main drivers are the supporting policies and an increasing general interest in sustainability.
- *What are biodegradable coatings or plastics degrading to?* Full degradation proof would be that the material is converted into CO₂ and some carbon-containing biomass. This shows that it is a completely safe product. However, as biodegradation is depending on the environment, this must always be demonstrated for the different environments. An example of a bio-based and biodegradable coating is PHA. This polymer does degrade in any natural environment.

4.1.4 Session 4: Industrial Applications

Session 4 on industrial aspects of the EU bioeconomy policy framework was kicked off by two speakers from the **European Commission, DG GROW**. Algreit Dume started by emphasising the importance of the Transition Pathway for the Chemical Industry to deliver the objectives of the Green Deal. The Pathway supports the business case for a green, digital, and resilient chemical industry. It has eight building blocks: sustainable competitiveness, investment and funding, research and innovation, regulation and public governance, access to energy and feedstock, infrastructures, skills and the social dimension. Now, the Commission is working together with stakeholders on the co-implementation of the Pathway. As part of this process, the Pathway is translated into concrete actions. The speaker illustrated the work done for the co-implementation such as setting up an expert group, “the Working Group on Chemical industry”, task forces focusing on high-priority topics such as energy and feedstock needs, and market pull measures for alternative feedstocks to fossil ones. In July 2023 a call for transition initiatives was launched. These are linked to the objectives of the Pathway. Now over 110 projects are included on the website of the Commission. Most projects (58%) are concentrated in Germany and 85% of the projects have a contribution from industry. The speaker continued by showing the regulatory roadmap of the Transition Pathway and the EU funding available to support projects, for example, the Just Transition Fund (€19 billion), the Innovation Fund (€40 billion) and Horizon Europe (€95 billion). He concluded that the Transitional Pathway for the Chemical Industry is a menu that solves the equation between fostering competitiveness and strengthening sustainability.

Maarit Nyman continued by presenting the workshops that the EC have been conducting on the topic of boosting biomanufacturing and the uptake of bio-based materials. The results of these workshops provided useful input for the communication “Building the Future with Nature” which was issued on 20 March 2024. The communication identifies the challenges and barriers and targeted actions to boost biotechnology and biomanufacturing in the EU. The report identified that, while the EU market size is large and growing, it is lagging far behind the US market. The main challenges identified were: transfer of the results of innovation research to the market, the regulatory complexity, access to finance, availability of skills, value chain obstacles such as, protection of intellectual property, public acceptance and economic security. The speaker summarised the actions on which DG GROW will be working in close cooperation with other DGs, such as carrying out a study on the simplification of the regulatory framework, creating an EU biotech hub to support companies navigate the regulation and available support, updating European standards and encouraging more private investments. Next steps are to implement the actions from the communication and continue the dialogue with stakeholders. Participants were invited to provide their feedback and share their ideas to support these next steps. One of the opportunities to do so is the GROW workshop “next steps in advancing bio-based products and materials” that is scheduled for 21 May.

Chloe Johnson from **the CBE JU and project officer for the CHAMPION project** continued with a presentation on how CBE JU is supporting innovation of sustainable bio-based materials and products. Following a brief introduction of CBE JU, the general objectives and the types of supported actions, she continued with an overview of the projects that have received support from CBE JU and the specific KPIs that these projects address. CBE JU has 8 application clusters, with both CHAMPION and PERFECOAT being included in the cluster named bio-based polymers / bio-based plastics. She concluded the presentation by providing an overview of the topics that are planned to be supported in the 2024 call for projects that is closing 18 Sept. 2024.

In the final presentation for the **CHAMPION project** Thomas Farmer from Unilever (and former scientific manager of the CHAMPION project) provided an overview on end-user application testing of polymers. He illustrated how the performance testing played a crucial role in the entire

project and how the industry partners were actively involved. He illustrated that the selection of candidates had been particularly challenging, starting with 180 candidates and 15 pre-polymers that went through preliminary property screening, then reduced to 69 candidates that progressed to initial performance testing and after this performance testing and toxicity testing was further reduced to a group of candidates

selected for end-of-life assessments. Finally four lead candidates remained that went through advanced testing. After Thomas provided further details on the selection process for each of the four application areas, Philippe Willems from Orineo, an industry partner in the CHAMPION project, provides an intermezzo in which he shows how some of the performance testing for application on hard surfaces have been conducted and the results obtained, and conclusions drawn. He concludes by pointing out that some of the materials that have been developed in the project are available in the exhibition room. Both speakers reach the conclusion that early testing by industry partners is essential for success.

The final presentation for the **PERFECOAT project** was provided by Simone Schulte from Evonik Coating Additives, who presented on bio-based coating formulation and application testing. After a brief overview on typical coating components, she explained how the basic properties had been tested and showed some of the testing results. A key conclusion is that the bio-based pigments could be processed and provide good colour development, but that the long-term stability of the colour is not yet sufficient. Incorporation of bio-based fillers could be easily achieved but the results for mechanical resistance show that improvement is needed. The bio-based micro fibrillated cellulose shows expected rheology modification as well as benefits in mud cracking performance. Addition of modified POSS leads to benefits in resistance. Finally, binder development is a more complex task.

The **final Q&A session** included a wide range of questions:

- *Does the European Commission also consider to implement a biomaterial directive to foster the use of bio-based materials in a wider range of sectors in the future?* This is not a policy that is under the remit of the transition pathways, but we are developing initiatives that also trigger increase of demand. Our activities comprise a wide range of policies, such as target setting, taxation, standards, and demand-pull policies. We are currently mapping the options and then in the next step we can consider which potential Directives would be implemented.
- *How are the outcomes of projects like PERFECOAT and CHAMPION and specifically the sustainability assessments considered by the Commission?* All the different types of feedback received that are related to bio-based materials are fed in the design of the policy measures, as has been done in the dialogue that was explained in the presentation. The project results are the foundation of the new policy measures.
- *Does CBE JU track and support the success of flagship plants developed as to ensure successful continuity to their mission?* Yes, we provide extensive support to the projects. Commercial application aspects we further support by means of promotion activities.
- *Is there a possibility for UK based SME's to be involved in CBE JU projects?* Yes, UK participants are now fully associated in Horizon Europe and in the CBE JU programmes.
- *Can you predict a timeline for further development of the materials developed in the CHAMPION project?* The project provided promising results in various aspects. There are challenges and remaining gaps, but it is unclear how long it will exactly take. It should be noted that the materials are benchmarked against materials that had a long time to improve their performance.
- *What is the most valuable lesson for PERFECOAT for new coatings?* As indicated by CHAMPION project, also the PERFECOAT project concludes that we have to include the industry partners as early as possible, in order to have a reality test on their applicability. Also the networking and exchange with similar projects such as CHAMPION is very valuable for supporting follow-up activities.
- *Do you think that one day the market would trade having a super white wall for more sustainable and healthy products?* Yes, we fully believe this will be achieved. It does however need time, money and resources to get there.

4.2 Use of interactive tool for Q&A

During the event the sli.do tool was used to support real-time question and answer (Q&A) sessions. This tool allowed the participants to submit questions to all speakers of each session and also vote on each other questions. Questions with the highest number of votes were read out by the session chairperson and answered by the relevant speaker in the Panel Q&A sessions. The questions asked to the speakers and their answers can be found in each of the Sessions in the previous section.

5 Dissemination activities and networking

5.1 Poster presentations

During the event a poster exhibition provided additional information to the participants on the projects presenting themselves at the event. Four of these posters were developed by the CHAMPION consortium (included in Annex 6):

1. **Chemical Recycling of Amine-crosslinked Polyesters.** This poster provided by University of York explains why and when chemical recycling makes sense, provides details on the steps involving of CHAMPION project materials, and an outlook on the feasibility of chemical recycling of CHAMPION materials.
2. **Projecting future commercial production.** This poster provided by PDC explains part of the work conducted in CHAMPION WP8, illustrating the conceptual process design, the typical scale-up challenges, and the techno-economic assessment.
3. **Scaling up of bio-based monomers and polymers.** This poster provided by VTT, in cooperation with Ava-Biochem, WFBR and Circa, explains part of the work conducted in CHAMPION WP5. It explains both the approach to and results of the scaling activities.
4. **Dissemination activities.** This poster, developed by SQ Consult in cooperation with University of York presents a selection of the dissemination activities including the webinars, fun green chemistry activities, newsletters, quizzes and the Green Kid comic book.

5.2 Exhibition of materials

Alongside the poster presentations both projects also displayed some of the products they have developed in the scope of their project activities. Participants were invited to check out the samples and feel their design qualities.

5.3 The Green Kid comic book

During the event the Green Kid comic book was presented and each of the participants received a copy. The comic book tells the story of fully sustainable wind turbines that have been developed with the CHAMPION system, so that are fully made from bio-based or recycled products, used only renewable energy when being produced, using non-toxic components that safely degrade at the end of life, and making sure that the adhesive switched off at the molecular level, so the materials can be reused. These innovative wind turbines are however sabotaged by a famous criminal. But the Green Kid comes to the rescue to show that click chemistry used in producing the blades of the wind turbine allow for re-use of the components and a successful operation of the wind turbines.

In addition to the lead story, the comic book also includes some explanations of circular economy, the science behind developing the CHAMPION polymers, a glossary of key terminology and some puzzles. The comic book will be distributed to scholars in several countries where CHAMPION partners are based.

The comic book was developed by three of the CHAMPION partners, WFBR, University of York and SQ Consult, with graphical design, art and production conducted by the Teesside University and the Green Chemistry explanations supported by the University of Lincoln.

A digital version is included Annex 7.

5.4 Networking opportunities

The dissemination activities described in the previous chapter aimed to share the work of the CHAMPION project team as well as provide networking opportunities with peers as to increase discussions on exploitation of the various results and increase follow-up opportunities.

In addition to networking cocktail at the end of the event, participants made grateful use of the lunch and coffee breaks for networking.

6 Conclusions

Based on the high participation and active discussions at the sold-out stakeholder event, the project team concludes that the final stakeholder event was successful. An elaborate, multi-pronged approach to communicating about the event and building an interesting agenda requires significant time investment but is well worth the effort. Scheduling an in-person event aimed at attracting an international audience back-to-back with another event with a similar target group can be recommended.

Active networking and the combination of an event with the exhibition was appreciated by the participants, and several participants had requested additional information on the project activities. The choice for co-organising the event with a second project – the PERFECOAT project – and inviting sibling projects to provide a presentation provided good added value, both in terms of the content and organisation.

Annex 1: Overview of participating organisations

Our stakeholder event “Bio-based innovations for industrial applications” was attended by 111 persons. For privacy reasons we list only the participating organizations below.

ADM BIOSOLUTIONS	European Commission	REDcert
AFRY	Fortum RW	Sanofi
Allnex	Ghent University	Sant’Anna School of
Arkema	GOVI	Advanced Studies
Asian paints ltd	Hezelburcht B.V.	SINTEF
ATTIX	IceTec	SINTEF Ocean
AXIA Innovation	Institut of Technology and	Sparxell
Bajer ConsultingS/canfibre	Life Sciences	SQ Consult
BASF	IRIS Coatings	Stahl
BETEK BOYA	Karel de Grote University	Sterimed Group
BGreen Technology	of Applied Sciences and	Syensqo
BioDetection Systems	Arts	Technical University of
British Sugar	Kastamonu Entegre	Munich
Brussels Municipality	Krahn Chemie	thyssenkrupp Steel Europe
BYK	Kraton Chemical B.V.	Tricon
Cadi Ayyad University	KUL	TU München CBR
Canon Production Printing	KURARAY	UAB
NL	Locus FS	ULB
CBE JU	Lubrizol	Unilever R&D Port Sunlight
CEA	Ludwig Maximilian	Universität Leipzig
Centre for Process	University of Munich	University of Antwerp
Innovation (CPI)	MBCC Investments	University of Turbat
CIRCE- Centro Tecnológico	Mohammed VI Polytechnic	University of York
Corbion	University Bengurir	VITO
CropEnergies AG	Nationwide paper	VTT
CSBR	NatureWorks Belgium	VUB
Daydream	Normec OWS	Wageningen Food &
De Monchy international	nova-Institute	Biobased Research
DEKRA e.V.	NovelYeast	wizemann:beratung
Elkem	Orac NV	Worlée Chemie
Endurans	ORINEO BV	
ePAPHOS ADVISORS	PaperInnovator	
TEAMWORK	Process Design Center	

Annex 2: Shared CHAMPION-PERFECOAT press release

Bio-based innovations for industrial applications: stakeholder event on 24 April 2024 in Brussels presents latest breakthroughs and key findings from research on circular bio-based solutions

Organised by two EU-funded research projects, CHAMPION and PERFECOAT, this stakeholder event is dedicated to the latest developments in bio-based solutions for various materials such as coatings, paints, adhesives and detergents.

Bio-based Innovations for Industrial Applications
24 April 2024, 09:00 – 17:00 CET

**BIP Meeting Center,
Rue Royale 2-4, B-1000 Brussels**
Free Registration • In-person Event

These projects receive funding from the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 887398 and No 101022370. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

The research projects [CHAMPION](#) and [PERFE COAT](#) aim to replace conventional fossil-based materials with novel bio-based solutions. At their jointly organised event, “Bio-based Innovations for Industrial Applications”, taking place on 24 April 2024 in Brussels, Belgium, both projects will present their recent findings and demonstrate the potential of the EU bioeconomy. This event will be held the day after the [CBE JU Info Day 2024](#) in Brussels.

The agenda includes dedicated sessions on novel bio-based compounds and applications, sustainability, safety and toxicity assessments, and a reality check for industrial applications. Speakers from the European Commission (EC) and Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU) will share the latest and upcoming sector developments. Covering a broad range of topics from policy to technology, the event offers a great platform to network with stakeholders and delve into pioneering developments in bio-based solutions.

The CHAMPION project focuses on bio-based thermoset coatings, structural adhesives, automotive interior surfaces and home care additives. In contrast, the PERFECOAT project targets the development of novel bio-based ingredients for paints and coatings to be used in high-volume, UV-curable clear coatings, waterborne trim paints for DIY and waterborne wall paint.

Topic-related European projects like 3-CO, HARMONITOR and LIGNICOAT will also present their findings in the quest for an innovative and sustainable EU economy. The event will be accompanied by a poster exhibition and end with a networking cocktail.

The full programme of the event has now been released.

Registration for the one-day event is free of charge at:

<https://events.renewable-carbon.eu/event/bio-based-innovations-for-industrial-applications>

Agenda “Bio-based Innovations for Industrial Applications”

Session 1: End-user perspectives on bio-based innovations

- **Janice Lofthouse** (University of York – CHAMPION) and **Francesca Di Bartolomeo** (SINTEF – PERFECOAT) – *Event Opening*
- **Daan van Es** (WFBR) – *An overview of the CHAMPION project*
- **Francesca Di Bartolomeo** (SINTEF) – *An introduction to the PERFECOAT project*
- **Marisa Groenestege** (BTG Biomass Technology Group – HARMONITOR project) – *Navigating trade and sustainability certification of bio-based value chains*
- **Costanza Rossi** (University of Utrecht – 3-CO project) – *What drives sustainability in businesses?*

Session 2: Making bio-based compounds

- **Oscar Bedzo** and **Lalitha Gottumukkala** (Celignis) – *Developing bio-based binders for wood coatings*
- **Rolf Blaauw** (WFBR) – *Bio-based polymer synthesis and scale-up*
- **Amelie Skopp** (Technische Universität München) and **Anders Odum** (Chromologics SA) – *Developing bio-based paint ingredients: from fillers to pigments and functional additives*
- **Claudio Pagella** (IRIS Coating – LIGNICOAT) – *Lignin-based clear fire protection biocoatings for wood*

Session 3: Sustainability, safety and toxicity

- **Harrie Besselink** (BioDetection Systems) – *Safety and toxicity assessments and methodology*
- **Sigrid Damman** and **Assiya Kenzhegaliyeva** (SINTEF Digital) – *Environmental and social sustainability assessment*
- **Maarit Nyman** and **Algreit Dume** (European Commission, DG GROW, Unit Bioeconomy, Chemicals & Cosmetics) – *Industrial aspects of the EU bioeconomy policy framework: recent developments*

Session 4: Industrial applications

- **Chloe Johnson** (CBE JU) – *Circular Bio-Based Europe JU: supporting innovation of sustainable bio-based materials and products*
- **Thomas Farmer** (Unilever) – *End-user application testing of polymers in CHAMPION*
- **Christine Louis** (Evonik) and **Roland Steinrücken** (Remmers) – *Bio-based coating formulation and application testing*
- **Steven Verstichel** (Normec OWS) – *Circularity and end-of-life options for biobased and biodegradable products*

Closure

- **Alexander Wetzel** (SINTEF) and **James Clark** (University of York's Green Chemistry Centre) – *Closing statement*
- **Maarit Nyman** (European Commission, DG GROW, Unit Bioeconomy, Chemicals & Cosmetics) – *Closing statement*

Networking cocktail (and poster exhibition)

Location:

BIP Meeting Center,

Rue Royale 2-4, B-1000 Brussels

The CHAMPION project has received funding from the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 887398. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

The PERFECOAT project has received funding from the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022370. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

Annex 3: Event flyer

Invitation
Stakeholder Event

Bio-based Innovations for Industrial Applications

24 APRIL 2024, 9:00–17:00

BIP Meeting Center

Rue Royale 2-4, B-1000 Brussels, Belgium

Explore the latest bio-based solutions for a variety of applications. The event combines presentations, a poster exhibition and plenty of opportunities for networking.

Speakers will include researchers involved in the development of new bio-based materials and representatives from industry, the European Commission and the CBE JU.

The organisers of the event, the BBI JU projects CHAMPION and PERFECOAT, aim to replace conventional fossil-based materials with novel bio-based solutions. The CHAMPION project focuses on bio-based thermoset coatings, structural adhesives, automotive interior surfaces and home care additives, while the PERFECOAT project is all about new bio-based ingredients for paints and coatings for wood and decorative applications.

This event will be held on 24 April 2024 in Brussels, one day after the CBE JU Info Day.

[Free Registration](#)

AGENDA

9:30 – 10:35

End-user Perspectives on Bio-based Innovations

- Event Opening
- An Overview of the CHAMPION project
- Navigating Trade and Sustainability Certification of Bio-based Value Chains
- What Drives Sustainability in Businesses?

10:50 – 12:15

Making Bio-based Compounds

- Developing Bio-based Binders for Wood Coatings
- Bio-based Polymer Synthesis and Scale-up
- Developing Bio-based Paint Ingredients: from Fillers to Pigments and Functional Additives
- Lignin-based Clear Fire Protection Biocoatings for Wood

13:15 – 14:30

Sustainability, Safety and Toxicity

- Safety and Toxicity Assessments and Methodology
- Environmental and Social Sustainability Assessment
- Industrial Aspects of the EU Bioeconomy Policy Framework: Recent Developments

14:30 – 15:45

Industrial Applications

- Circular Bio-Based Europe JU: Supporting Innovation of Sustainable Bio-based Materials and Products
- End-user Application Testing of Polymers in CHAMPION
- Bio-based Coating Formulation and Application Testing
- Circularity and End-of-life Options for Bio-based and Biodegradable Products

Annex 4: Event agenda

Agenda

Stakeholder Event
**Bio-based Innovations for
Industrial Applications**

BIP Meeting Center,
Rue Royale 2-4, B-1000 Brussels
April 24, 2024

Join at sli.do for Real Time Questions and Comments

To vote on which questions will be asked to the speakers
and to ask your own, go to app.sli.do/event/champer

#CHAMPER

WEDNESDAY

April 24, 2024

9:00 – 9:30 Registration and Welcome Coffee

9:30 – 10:35

Session 1:
End-user Perspectives on Bio-based Innovations

9:30

Janice Lofthouse (University of York – CHAMPION) and
Francesca di Bartolomeo (SINTEF – PERFECOAT)
Event Opening

9:35

Daan van Es (WFBR)
An Overview of the CHAMPION Project

9:45

Francesca di Bartolomeo (SINTEF)
An Introduction to the PERFECOAT Project

9:55

Marisa Groenestege (BTG Biomass Technology Group – HARMONITOR Project)
Navigating Trade and Sustainability Certification of Bio-based Value Chains

10:10

Costanza Rossi (University of Utrecht – 3-CO project)
What Drives Sustainability in Businesses?

10:25

Panel Q&A for Session 1

10:35 – 10:55

Coffee Break

10:55 – 12:15

Session 2:
Making Bio-based Compounds

10:55

Oscar Bedzo and Lalitha Gottumukkala (Celignis)
Developing Bio-based Binders for Wood Coatings

11:10

Rolf Blaauw (WFBR)
Bio-based Polymer Synthesis and Scale-up

11:25

Amelie Skopp (Technische Universität München) and
Anders Odum (Chromologics SA)
**Developing Bio-based Paint Ingredients: from Fillers to Pigments
and Functional Additives**

11:40

Claudio Pagella (IRIS Coating – LIGNICOAT)
Lignin-based Clear Fire Protection Biocoatings for Wood

11:55

Panel Q&A for Session 2

12:15 – 13:15

Light Lunch and Networking including Poster Exhibition

Join at sli.do for Real Time Questions and Comments

To vote on which questions will be asked to the speakers and to ask your own, go to app.sli.do/event/champer

#CHAMPER

13:15 – 14:25	
Session 3: Sustainability, Safety and Toxicity	
13:15	Harrie Besselink (BioDetection Systems) and Andy Booth (SINTEF) Safety and Toxicity Assessments and Methodology
13:35	Ángel Puente (nova-Institute) and Assiya Kenzhgaliyeva (SINTEF Digital) Environmental and Social Sustainability Assessment
13:55	Steven Verstichel (Normec OWS) Circularity and End-of-life Options for Bio-based and Biodegradable Products

14:10 Panel Q&A for Session 3

14:25 – 15:50	
Session 4: Industrial Applications	
14:25	Maarit Nyman and Algreit Dume (European Commission) Industrial Aspects of the EU Bioeconomy Policy Framework: Recent Developments
14:45	Chloe Johnson (CBE JU) Circular Bio-Based Europe JU: Supporting Innovation of Sustainable Bio-based Materials and Products
15:00	Thomas Farmer (Unilever) End-user Application Testing of Polymers in CHAMPION
15:15	Simone Schulte (Evonik Coating Additives) Bio-based Coating Formulation and Application Testing

15:30 Panel Q&A for Session 4

15:50 – 16:00	
Closure	
15:50	Alexander Wetzel (SINTEF) and James Clark (University of York's Green Chemistry Centre) Closing Statement

16:00 – 17:00 Networking Cocktail (and Poster Exhibition)

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

The CHAMPION project has received funding from the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 887398. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

The PERFECOAT project has received funding from the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022370. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

Annex 5: Presentations at the stakeholder event

PDFs of all presentations have been posted on the CHAMPION website. Including them directly in this document would make it unwieldy, therefore we provide the links below.

Session 1: End-user perspectives on bio-based innovations

- [*An overview of the CHAMPION project*](#) – Daan van Es (WFBR – CHAMPION project)
- [*An introduction to the PERFECOAT project*](#) – Francesca Di Bartolomeo (SINTEF – PERFECOAT project)
- [*Navigating trade and sustainability certification of bio-based value chains*](#) – Marisa Groenestege (BTG Biomass Technology Group – HARMONITOR project)
- [*What drives sustainability in businesses?*](#) – Costanza Rossi (University of Utrecht – 3-CO project)

Session 2: Making bio-based compounds

- [*Developing bio-based binders for wood coatings*](#) – Oscar Bedzo (Celignis – PERFECOAT project)
- [*Bio-based polymer synthesis and scale-up*](#) – Rolf Blaauw (WFBR – CHAMPION project)
- [*Developing bio-based paint ingredients: from fillers to pigments and functional additives*](#) – Amelie Skopp (Technische Universität München) and Anders Odum (Chromologics SA) – PERFECOAT project
- [*Lignin-based clear fire protection biocoatings for wood*](#) – Claudio Pagella (IRIS Coating – LIGNICOAT project)

Session 3: Sustainability, safety and toxicity

- [*Safety and toxicity assessments and methodology*](#) – Harrie Besselink (Bio Detection Systems – CHAMPION project) and Andy Booth (SINTEF – PERFECOAT project)
- [*Environmental and social sustainability assessment*](#) – Assiya Kenzhegaliyeva (SINTEF Digital – PERFECOAT project) and Angel Puente (nova-Institute – CHAMPION project)
- [*Circularity and end-of-life options for biobased and biodegradable products*](#) – Steven Verstichel (Normec OWS – CHAMPION project)

Session 4: Industrial applications

- [*Industrial aspects of the EU bioeconomy policy framework: recent developments*](#) – Maarit Nyman and Algreit Dume (European Commission, DG GROW, Unit Bioeconomy, Chemicals & Cosmetics)
- [*Circular Bio-Based Europe JU: supporting innovation of sustainable bio-based materials and products*](#) – Chloe Johnson (CBE JU)
- [*End-user application testing of polymers in CHAMPION*](#) – Thomas Farmer (Unilever – CHAMPION project)
- [*Bio-based coating formulation and application testing*](#) – Simone Schulte (Evonik) – PERFECOAT project

Annex 6: Posters presented at the poster session

PDFs of all posters have been posted on the CHAMPION website. Including them directly in this document would make it unwieldy, therefore we provide the links below.

- **CHAMPION project:**
 - [Chemical recycling of amine-crosslinked polyesters](#)
 - [Scaling up of bio-based monomers and polymers](#)
 - [Projecting future commercial production](#)
 - [CHAMPION quizzes, comic and webinars](#)
- **PERFECOAT project:**
 - [PERFECOAT – High performance bio-based functional coatings for wood and decorative applications](#)
 - [The beauty of green – Rethinking an approach to bio-based extenders in coating](#)
 - [Bio-based coating formulation and application testing](#)
 - [Development of microbial alginate and oils productions](#)
 - [Development of biobased pigments and functional materials](#)
- **HARMONITOR project:**
 - [Harmonisation and monitoring platform for certification schemes and labels to advance the sustainability of bio-based systems](#)
- **LIGNICOAT project:**
 - [Clear fire-retardant lignin-based biocoatings](#)

Annex 7: CHAMPION's issue of the Green Kid comic

FREE
#5

UNIVERSITY OF LINCOLN AND TEESIDE
UNIVERSITY PRESENT

GREENKID

SCIENCE! PUZZLES! THIS ISSUE: A FAMILIAR FACE STRIKES BACK! ALL THIS AND MORE.

GLOSSARY

AMINES - CHEMICALS THAT HAVE A NITROGEN ATOM THAT IS ATTACHED TO A CARBON ATOM THAT ITSELF IS ONLY ATTACHED TO OTHER CARBONS OR HYDROGENS.

BIODERIVED - ANYTHING WHERE THE ORIGINAL CARBON SOURCE IS CO₂, THAT IS THEN CONVERTED INTO SOMETHING ELSE BY A LIVING ORGANISM E.G. PLANTS TAKE CO₂ AND WATER TO MAKE SUGARS.

CARBON-CARBON DOUBLE BOND - WHEN TWO CARBON ATOMS ARE JOINED TOGETHER BY TWO BONDS (THIS IS WHAT MAKES SOME OILS/FATS BE CALLED UNSATURATED). THE SECOND BOND IS A BIT WEAKER SO IT CAN BE OPENED TO MAKE NEW COMPOUNDS.

CHAMPION - AN EU FUNDED PROJECT LOOKING AT PRODUCING SAFE, BIO-DERIVED POLYMERS AND SWITCHABLE ADHESIVES.

CIRCULAR ECONOMY - A CLOSED LOOP, AT THE END OF LIFE, THINGS CAN BE MADE INTO SOMETHING NEW.

ECO WIND TURBINE - A WIND TURBINE THAT HAS BEEN DESIGNED FOR EASY REUSE/RECYCLING OF ITS COMPONENT PARTS AT THE END OF LIFE.

THERMOPLAST - A PLASTIC/POLYMER THAT IS HARD AT ROOM TEMPERATURE BUT CAN BE RESHAPED OR REMOULDED WHEN HOT. THESE TYPES OF POLYMER CAN BE EASILY RECYCLED.

THERMOSET - A PLASTIC/POLYMER THAT WHEN REACTED WITH A CROSS-LINKER FORMS NEW BONDS BETWEEN THE POLYMER CHAINS, WE CALL THIS CURING. ONCE CURED, THIS TYPE OF POLYMER IS VERY TOUGH BUT USUALLY ALSO VERY HARD TO RECYCLE.

science!
with
Dr. Science!
COLOUR THE COMIC!

HHHHMMMMMMMM!!!!

ZZZMM!

THE-
THE BLADES!

BOBBY!
LOOK
OUT!

WHOOOSH!!!!

I'M
OKAY!

NO!
NO!
NO!
WHAT
HAVE I
DONE!

WHAT THE
HECK COULD
HAVE CREATED
SUCH A STRONG
GUST OF...

YOU'VE
GOT TO BE
KIDDING
ME...

WHUD!
WHUD!
WHUD!
WHUD!

SUMMER,
GREEN KID!
IT'S BEEN TOO
LONG!

DID
YOU MISS
ME?

*EDITOR'S NOTE:
SEE GREEN KID ISSUE
3 FOR THE FIRST
APPEARANCE
OF DEL ALLEN.

DEL
ALLEN?!

BUT WE
SENT YOU TO
PRISON FOR ALL
THOSE CRIMES YOU
COMMITTED!

FORTUNATELY
I WAS EXONERATED
ON ALL CHARGES.

UNFORTUNATELY,
I COULD HAVE PREVENTED THIS
DISASTER HAD I NOT BEEN
TIED UP WITH ALL OF THAT
NONSENSE.

WHILE THE RESINS CREATED BY
CHAMPION SOUND LIKE A
GOOD IDEA IN PRINCIPLE THEY'RE
JUST NOT AS RELIABLE AND STURDY
AS THE GOOD OLD FASHIONED
ENGINEERING THAT KEEPS
RENEWABLE ALLEN TECH
TOGETHER.

JUST AS I SUSPECTED!

ALLEN'S TECH IS IMPRESSIVE, BEING ABLE TO EMIT A BEAM OF ENERGY FROM ABOUT A MILE AWAY AT WELL OVER 200 DEGREES CENTIGRADE.

ENOUGH TO TURN THE CHAMPION RESIN FROM A THERMOSET* TO A THERMOPLAST*.

NOW ALL WE NEED TO DO IS FIGURE OUT HOW TO BRING THIS TO LIGHT.

I FEEL LIKE WE SHOULD PRIORITISE GETTING THOSE WIND TURBINES BACK RUNNING.

ALL THOSE HOMES ARE WITHOUT RENEWABLE POWER UNTIL ALLEN'S ROBOT COMES ONLINE.

YEAH BUT HOW ARE WE GONNA GET THOSE BLADES BACK ON THERE?

I GUESS WE GOTTA ASK THE EXPERT.

THE NEXT MORNING.

SO ALLEN USED A LONG RANGE HEAT RAY TO DESTROY MY WIND TURBINE?

I THOUGHT IT WAS JUST ME MESSING UP AGAIN.

YOU DID EVERYTHING RIGHT WILLIAM.

YOU JUST DIDN'T ACCOUNT FOR A SOCIOPATH WITH MORE MONEY THAN GOD AND A GRUDGE AGAINST ME AND GREEN KID, TURNING UP WITH A GIANT DEATH RAY ROBOT!

I THINK THIS GOES BEYOND YOUR AVERAGE RISK ASSESSMENT.

GREEN KID AND I HAVE A PLAN TO RETRIEVE THE BLADES FROM THE WATER BUT WE'LL NEED YOU TO HELP US RE-ATTACH THEM.

RE-ATTACH THEM? THE WHOLE THING WILL NEED TO GO BACK TO THE MANUFACTURING STAGE.

NOT NECESSARILY.

UGH!
IS IT ME OR IS IT GETTING HOT IN HERE?

SIR!
SYSTEMS ARE FAILING, WE'RE GOING DOWN!

THEY SAY THAT YOU'RE A TECH REVOLUTIONARY ALLEN,
I JUST SAY YOU'RE ALL WASHED UP.
SERIOUSLY? YOU'RE DOING DAD JOKES NOW?

WILLIAM, ONCE WE FOUND EVIDENCE THAT YOU'D BEEN SABOTAGED THERE WAS SOMEONE WE NEEDED TO CONTACT FIRST.

WILLIAM, HEY LISTEN, WE'RE REALLY SORRY.

WE SHOULD HAVE HAD MORE FAITH IN YOU.
WE SHOULDN'T HAVE DOUBTED YOU.

WELL I APPRECIATE THE APOLOGY.
I GUESS I'M NOT SUCH A LOSER AFTER ALL.

YOU'RE NOT A LOSER.

YOU'RE A CHAMPION.

THE END

You can also chemically recycle PET to make it just like new. You turn the plastic back into the monomers that it was made from and make new plastic. This takes more energy but it can be done as many times as you like.

CHAMPION is making safe, renewable switchable adhesives so you can take things apart at their end of life. This means bits can be reused or recycled much more easily, a **circular economy**.

WORD SEARCH

D	T	A	I	B	N	T	T	U	R	B	I	N	E
N	A	O	R	S	A	L	C	A	S	H	A	R	C
I	T	H	E	R	M	O	P	L	A	S	T	A	D
W	B	E	O	C	T	B	L	I	E	O	R	T	N
O	S	N	D	E	A	E	A	E	N	B	E	H	O
C	C	A	N	E	O	E	I	C	O	S	E	N	B
E	H	O	N	O	V	B	V	N	O	R	H	W	E
B	A	I	O	M	T	I	C	M	C	B	T	R	L
A	M	W	H	N	C	A	R	I	E	B	R	O	B
M	P	R	V	E	R	E	O	E	S	P	N	B	U
I	I	N	D	B	H	D	M	E	D	A	H	T	O
N	O	R	O	T	N	M	A	E	N	O	B	I	D
E	N	N	R	W	A	I	U	N	U	O	I	I	I
S	R	E	E	N	B	O	C	M	T	D	R	B	A

- AMINES
- BIODERIVED
- CARBON CARBON
- DOUBLE BOND
- CHAMPION
- CIRCULAR ECONOMY
- ECO WIND
- TURBINE
- THERMOPLAST
- THERMOSET

HELP SPROUT GET BACK TO CYRUS!

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